

Paper 4

PROFESSIONAL SKILL TABLE FOR JOB SEEKING CAMPUS GRADUATES

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Abstract

Employability Skill set is the most important factor that any employer or recruiter shall look in a graduate for offering first job. Working Skills at industry is expected to be developed by the student during his/her tenure of academic study at graduating campus. This employability skill set cultivated by the job seeking graduate at campus should enable the student to clear interviews and also enable him/her sustain in first or new job. Therefore, this paper aims to investigate through Literature review, data collections from industry sources, and focus group interviews with expert panels, the list of employability skills which a job seeking graduate student at academic campus should possess while graduating out. The skill sets so identified will be created into a table which would expected to serve as a ready-made checklist for the stakeholders to reap the benefits.

Keywords: Employability Skills, Campus Graduates, Job Placement, Skill Development, Professional Skills.

I. Introduction :

Without a clear thought on exact kind of employability skills required for job seeking graduates, it is hard for stakeholders to determine in devising right kind of training mix activities to be imparted to students at Higher Educational Institution campuses. Circumstances are more often that Institution's time and money are invested in paying external skill trainers who charge in exorbitant fee to institutions with very less value add to student skill. This maybe due to an individual's ability to apply knowledge at interviews pertaining to use know-how to complete tasks, solve problems depends on personal intelligence, virtue, capacity, capability and competency. In pursuit of profit and sustainability, industries find lack of time either to spend at

educational campuses to prescribe cognitive ability of work involving the use of logical, intuitive, and creative thinking or practical work ability involving manual dexterity and the use of methods, materials, tools and instruments. This has kept the age inception old industry-academia gap intact with academia in ambiguity regarding the correct exact skills required for a fresh graduating student to clear employment interviews and sustain in careers. Hence, a Employability Skill Set Chart for students is necessitated here in this research paper for identification of key professional skills either to seek jobs by clearing interviews and sustain in work positions as well.

II. Objectives :

Primary aim of this paper is to present sets of Skill constructs necessary to serve as base for imparting and designing student employment training programs at campus. The Study also seeks to aid and support the Training and Placement Cell's of HEI (Higher Educational Institutions) in their quest for imparting skill focus based employment training.

III. Research Methodology :

To conduct the fundamental enquiry for this study, Scholarly Review of Literature was deployed to identify the skill sets. A Focus Group Interview was followed on experts from various sectors through random sampling. The solicited responses also contributed in designing the skill constructs mandating the competency, capability and capacity required for fresh graduates necessitating to perform work tasks.

IV. Analysis & Interpretation :

Table 1 : Skill Constructs Identified for Professional Skills via Scholarly Review of Literature

S. No	Skills	Literary Source
1.	Professional, Effective OR Business Communication	(Jablin, 1979) (Zhao & Rosson, 2009) (Triandis, 1959)
2.	Working-Disposition	(Clarke, 2002) (Jeffs, Tony, & Smith., 1994) (Cheng & Ho, 2001)

3.	Planning and Organizing	(Whitley, 1989) (Henderson & Venkatraman, 1993) (Rainsbury, Hodges, Burchell, & Lay, 2002) (Jackson, 2010)
4.	Learner, Flexible and Adaptable	(Freudenberg, Brimble, & Cameron, 2011) (Merriam, Caffarella, & Baumgartner, 2012) (Pearson & Brew, 2002) (Bell & Kozlowski, 2008)
5.	Critical Thinker and Problem Shooter	(Brown & Duguid, 1991) (Button, Mathieu, & (CT&PS) Zajac, 1996) (Rauen, 2001) (Halpern, 2001) (Lee, Trauth, & Farwell, 1995
6.	Team or Group Working	(Paskevich, Dorsch, & Widmeyer, 1999) (Aasheim, 2009) (Cappel, 2001-2002) (Shields, Gardner, Bredemeier, & Bostrom, 1995)
7.	Initiative Taker, Self-Management and Enterprising	(Manz & Sims, 1980) (Cheng & Ho, 2001) (IES) (Chiaburu & Tekleab,

		2005) (Cohen, 1990)
8.	Technology	(Von Tunzelmann & Acha, 2005) (Baroudi & Ginzberg, 1986) (Cappel, 2001-2002)

Table 2 : Focus Group Interview Respondent Result from Expert Panel consisting of Skill Typologies required :

Capacity, Capability and Competency		
Innovation and Creativity	Interest, Confidence and Attitude	Systems and Design Thinking

V. Findings :

In addition to the results of skill requirements published above in Table 1 and 2, the expert panel also expressed suggestions to design Full-Time Research Based Degree Courses or Practicum based Degree Courses whose curricula to be in alignment with above skill sets. Internships and Projects should be made as a quintessential credits for atleast 2 full semesters or years as apprenticeship focusing on vocational skills. Consequently, student motivation can be achieved when the trainee and trainer works with the same synergy and strengths and weakness are realized before-hand. Motivation however here is typically defined as a variability in behaviour not attributable to stable individual differences.

VI. Conclusions :

In this research, we have gathered the list of professional skill sets necessary for a graduate to possess for clearing campus interviews and also sustain in the employment. The Skill constructs also supports the design and device Training Programs, MOOCs, and Training Syllabus Contents at educational institution campuses. Finally, though individual differences like cognitive abilities of job seeking graduates may not affect their training motivation, but it appears that the behaviour, interest, consent, preparedness of the individual graduate and the existing campus and job market environment affect it greatly.

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